

A Study of Intestinal Stomas: It's Indications and Complications**Mudit Pathak¹, Neha Shukla², Snehlata Katare³**¹Surgical Specialist, Government District Hospital, Datia, MP, India²Senior Resident, Department of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprosy, GRMC Gwalior, MP, India³Government Medical Officer, Ophthalmology, Datia, MP, India

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Abstract:

Background: Stomas may be 'permanent' which are created indefinitely or 'temporary' which can be closed later. In case of intestinal perforation and obstruction, it is always a difficult decision for a surgeon to create a stoma for fecal diversion. Intestinal stoma surgery is lifesaving procedure, as a surgeon we should cope with emotional and functional impairment that a patient undergoes intestinal stoma surgery particularly in the early postoperative period. This is why any recommendation and suggestions in the management of stoma, or change in surgical technique, which seem to have merit should be accepted by patient, attenders, nursing staff and surgeon and hence is the need for study on indications & complications of intestinal stomas and their management.

Objectives: To study indications and various complications of intestinal stomas.

Methodology: From November 2018 to June 2020, 61 patients from the general surgery, surgical gastroenterology, and pediatric surgery departments of RD Gardi Medical College Ujjain participated in the study. The study aimed to determine the many kinds of intestinal stomas and their indications, as well as the different consequences that were experienced and how they may be reduced and better controlled. The study included all patients undergoing stoma creation, male and female, up to the age of 70.

Results: The age group of 30 to 40 years old had the highest number of cases. It demonstrates a highly significant correlation ($p < 0.01$) between the patient's age and the stoma construction. Most people in the 30- to 40-year-old age range are at risk of having a loop ileostomy. 61 patients' lengths of hospital stays were examined; the majority (72.1%) spent between 10 and 20 days in the hospital. Skin excoriations were the most frequent consequence seen during stoma construction (45.9%), followed by laparotomy wound infection (13.1%). It demonstrates a substantial correlation ($p < 0.05$) between the indication for a stoma and difficulties resulting from its construction.

Conclusion: Most of the patients underwent stoma as an emergency procedure rather than elective procedure. Duration of hospital stay was approximately 10-20 days, even prolonged when complications occurred. The most common indications for stoma construction were hollow viscous perforation and enteric fever. Most common stoma constructed was loop ileostomy followed by end ileostomy. There is high incidence of peristomal complication related to that. The complications are better managed with proper preoperative planning and effective stoma care in post-operative period.

Keywords: Stoma; intestinal; indications; complications.

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Introduction

Stoma is an artificial opening or mouth like projection to the exterior of the abdominal wall. [1] An intestinal stoma is the opening of intestinal tract on the abdominal wall constructed surgically or appearing inadvertently. [2]

The purpose of stomas is to divert the faeces away from distal bowel loop to relieve the obstruction. It provides quick and effective management of emergencies like perforation peritonitis, intestinal obstruction due to different pathologies like enteric fever, Koch's abdomen, trauma abdomen, abdominal sepsis and also to provide management

of chronic conditions involving distal GIT like Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis and colorectal cancer. [3] Stomas may be 'permanent' which are created indefinitely or 'temporary' which can be closed later. [4] In case of intestinal perforation and obstruction, it is always a difficult decision for a surgeon to create a stoma for fecal diversion. Explaining its need to patient and attendant is rather more difficult. [5]

There may be many complications of intestinal stoma; stomal retraction, prolapse, necrosis para-ileostomy infection, abscess, fistula, intestinal

obstruction, skin irritation, excoriation mucosal ulceration, offensive odors prestomal ileitis, diarrhea, hemorrhage, costly ileostomy appliances, further closure surgery adds on to financial burden. [6] The majority of difficulties can be avoided by placing the stoma carefully and thoughtfully and by taking the necessary time to get adequate length to bring the stoma through the abdominal wall. The stoma should pass through the rectus abdominal muscle and is positioned behind the anterior superior iliac crest, which is typically the belt line. To ensure that the stoma plate fits properly, large scars and indentations in the abdomen wall should be avoided. [7] After a lengthy procedure, it is usual to feel tempted to mobilize a stoma that is not long enough.

One of two issues will almost invariably follow: either skin-level stenosis or stoma retraction. Similarly, very forceful mobilization may cause the stoma to necrotize. Stomal problems, such as peristomal hernias, fistulas from Crohn's disease, prolapse, or stricture, usually appear in the first few weeks following surgery but can also happen five or ten years later.

Approximately 20% of patients will eventually need a stoma-related reoperation. [8] Intestinal stoma surgery is lifesaving procedure, as a surgeon we should cope with emotional and functional impairment that a patient undergoes intestinal stoma surgery particularly in the early postoperative period. This is why any recommendation and suggestions in the management of stoma, or change in surgical technique, which seem to have merit should be accepted by patient, attenders, nursing staff and surgeon and hence is the need for study on indications & complications of intestinal stomas and their management.

Objectives: To study indications and various complications of intestinal stomas.

Material and Methods:

In this observational study, 61 patients who had intestinal stoma surgery between November 2018 and June 2020 were admitted to the RD Gardi Medical College in Ujjain, Madhya Pradesh, and

had surgery in the departments of general surgery, surgical gastroenterology, surgical oncology, and pediatric surgery. Every case had a thorough preoperative evaluation, and all preoperative findings, stoma building indications, postoperative complications, and various stoma formation-related issues were properly documented in accordance with protocol.

Sample Size: We applied the following calculation to determine the sample size based on the prevalence with a 95% confidence level:

$$n = z^2 * P * (100 - P) / d^2$$

Where the 95% confidence range for Z is 1.96.

P = 52.4% {Complications rate (SKIN EXCORIATION) is 52.4%}

L = 15 % absolute error

$$n = (1.96 * 1.96) * 52.4 * (100 - 52.4) / 15^2$$

n = 48 cases, and we took 61 cases in our study.

Inclusion Criteria:

- All patients male and female with age less than 70 years undergoing laparotomy. Followed by intestinal stomas construction.
- All emergency and elective instances involving the creation of intestinal stomas.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patient undergoing urinary stoma construction.
- Patient undergoing as an indication for gynecological disorders.
- Psychological complications are excluded

Study variables: Age, sex, nutrition, type of stoma surgery, mode of surgery, hospital stay, indications, and complications of stoma.

Statistical analysis: Obtained data were entered in Microsoft excel sheet 2007 and analysis was done by using epi info 7.2.0.1 version. Chi Square test was used to test associations between categorical variables, p value less than 0.05 were considered as level of significance for all tests of association.

Observation and Results:

Table 1: Age-Wise Distribution of Intestinal Stoma Surgery

Age Group (in years)	No.	Percent
<10	2	3.3
10 – 20	6	9.8
20 – 30	11	18.0
30 – 40	15	24.6
40 – 50	11	18.0
50 – 60	10	16.4
60 – 70	6	9.8
Total	61	100.0

Our study included 61 patients who underwent intestinal stoma surgery for various indications. The maximum no. of patients in Age group 30-40 years. This study had 44 male patients and 17 female patients.

Table 2: Mode of Surgery

Mode of Surgery	Frequency	Percent
Elective	9	14.8
Emergency	52	85.2
Total	61	100.0

Of the 61 patients, 52 received elective stoma construction, while 9 patients had stoma construction as an emergency treatment. The majority of patients were hospitalized for roughly 11 to 20 days (72.1%).

Table 3: Primary Indications for Intestinal Stoma

Primary Cause	Frequency	Percent
Enteric Fever	11	18.0
Necrotising Pancreatitis	1	1.6
Koch's Abdomen	4	6.6
Ileocecal Volvulus	1	1.6
Carcinoma Anal Canal	2	3.3
Stab Injury Abdomen	4	6.6
Strangulated Hernia	1	1.6
Iatrogenic	1	1.6
Anorectal Malformation	1	1.6
Mesenteric Ischemia	2	3.3
High Ano-Rectal Fistula	1	1.6
Carcinoma Rectum	5	8.2
Anastomotic Leak	1	1.6
Abdominal Sepsis	1	1.6
Hollow Viscus Perforation	19	31.1
Blunt Trauma Abdomen	2	3.3
Adhesive Intestinal Obstruction	2	3.3
Refractory Ulcerative Colitis	1	1.6
Gangrenous Volvulus	1	1.6
Total	61	100.0

The most frequent reasons for constructing a stoma were hollow viscous perforation (19%), enteric fever (11%), and GIT cancer (7%).

Table 4: Secondary Cause of Intestinal Stoma

Secondary causes	Frequency	Percent
Colonic Perforation	4	6.6
Fistula in Ano	1	1.6
Ileal gangrene	1	1.6
Ileal Perforation	32	52.5
Imperforated Anus	1	1.6
Intestinal gangrene	3	4.9
Intestinal Obstruction	12	19.7
Meckels Diverticulum	1	1.6
Small Bowel Laceration	1	1.6
Transverse colon Perforation	1	1.6
Total	57	93.4
Same as primary cause	4	6.6
Total	61	100.0

Intestinal perforation (52.5%), whether traumatic or infectious, was the most frequent reason for stoma creation among the 61 patients who had the procedure, followed by intestinal obstruction (19.7%).

Table 5: Type of Stoma

Type of stoma	Frequency	Percent
End Ileostomy	10	16.4
End Sigmoid Colostomy	1	1.6
End Sigmoid Colostomy with APR	6	9.8
Loop Ileostomy	41	67.2
Loop Sigmoid Colostomy	3	4.9
Total	61	100.0

Ileostomy was the most frequently performed stoma type among the 61 patients (83.6%). The most common ileostomy procedure was loop ileostomy (67.2%), which was followed by end ileostomy (16.4%). The most prevalent kind of colostomy was end sigmoid (11.4%), which was followed by loop sigmoid (4.9%).

Table 6: Complications and Type of Stoma

Complications	Type of stoma					Total
	End Ileostomy	End Sigmoid Colostomy	End Sigmoid Colostomy With Apr	Loop Ileostomy	Loop Sigmoid Colostomy	
Burst Abdomen, Stoma Bleeding	1	0	0	0	0	1
Intestinal Obstruction	1	0	0	0	0	1
Intestinal Obstruction Wound Infection	0	0	1	0	0	1
Mucosal Prolapse	0	0	0	2	0	2
Nill	1	0	1	11	3	16
Parastomal Abscess	0	0	0	1	0	1
Parastomal Abscess, Skin Excoriation	0	0	0	1	0	1
Retraction, Skin Excoriation	1	0	1	1	0	3
Skin Excoriation	2	1	2	12	0	17
Stoma Bleeding	1	0	0	0	0	1
Stoma Prolapse	0	0	0	1	0	1
Stoma Retraction	0	0	1	1	0	2
Stomal Necrosis	1	0	0	0	0	1
Stomal Prolapse, Skin Excoriation	0	0	0	1	0	1
Stomal Retraction, Skin Excoriation	0	0	0	1	0	1
Stomal Stenosis	1	0	0	1	0	2
Wound Infection	0	0	0	2	0	2
Wound Infection ,Burst Abdomen	0	0	0	1	0	1
Wound Infection And Skin Excoriation	0	0	0	3	0	3
Wound Infection Stomal Necrosis	1	0	0	0	0	1
Wound Infection, Skin Excoriation	0	0	0	2	0	2
Total	10	1	6	41	3	61

	Value	Of	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	61.247a	80	.941
Likelihood Ratio	50.209	80	.996
N of Valid Cases	61		

Every one of the 100 patients had their relationship to the stoma and any issues resulting from its construction examined. It demonstrates a substantial correlation ($p < 0.05$) between the indication for a stoma and difficulties resulting from its construction. Skin excoriation was the most frequent consequence, and it is more serious in loop ileostomy.

Table 7: Temporary and Permanent Intestinal Stomas and Mode of Surgery

Mode of Surgery	Type of Stoma		Total
	End Ileostomy and Colostomy	Loop Ileostomy	
Elective	9	0	9
Emergency	11	41	52
Total	20	41	61

	Value	Df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	21.643a	1	.000		
Continuity Correction	18.213	1	.000		
Likelihood Ratio	23.522	1	.000		
Fisher's Exact Test				.000	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	21.288	1	.000		
N of Valid Cases	61				

The most frequently recommended temporary stoma is loop ileostomy, which is advised mostly for emergency basis procedures with a highly significant P-value (<.01), while the majority of permanent intestinal stomas, including end colostomies and end ileostomies, are indicated primarily for elective surgeries.

Discussion

Stoma production has been a crucial life-saving technique since ancient times. The indications for stoma development have changed throughout time. In the past, intestinal blockage and combat injuries were the most frequent reasons for stoma creation. These days, the indications range from intestine perforation and obstruction brought on by different GIT diseases to malignant disorders including colorectal and colonic cancers. The morbidity and mortality rates linked with stomas were high due to the consequences. Instead of stoma development, primary anastomosis is the norm these days. However, in circumstances when surgery is not an option, stomas can still be useful for preventing anastomosis leaks and diverting feces. This study included patients who underwent surgery for various indications and intestinal stoma construction. The maximum number of patients were in the group of 30-40 years age (24.6%) followed by age groups 40-50 & 20-30, (18% for each). The association between stoma and age was examined for each of the 61 individuals. It demonstrates a highly significant correlation ($p < 0.01$) between the patient's age and the stoma construction. The majority of people in the 30-40 age range are at risk of having intestinal stoma surgery, specifically loop ileostomy. Patients of Age group 60-70 years are likely undergoes End sigmoid colostomy. Comparing to result of study "A clinico-observational study of intestinal stoma and their complications" by Shyam Bhutra et al., 31-35 yr is common age group for distribution of intestinal stoma surgery, [8] results are similar. Of the patients in this study, 28% were female and 72% were male. This suggests that compared to the

female population, male patients had more stomas constructed. All 61 individuals were examined in regard to their sex and stoma. It indicates that the patient's sex and stoma architecture have a less significant link ($p > 0.05$). So there is poor correlation with sex of the patient and stoma construction. Comparing to result of other studies on intestinal stoma surgery regarding sex distribution of stoma patients, study showing similar result but p-value is insignificant. [9] The association between the stoma and the surgical technique was examined for each of the 61 patients. It demonstrates that the mode of surgery and stoma creation have a strong and significant link ($p < 0.01$). Instead of being a discretionary treatment, the majority of patients have stomas done as an emergency. Loop ileostomy constituted the majority of the emergency procedure. End colostomy was the most often used stoma in elective procedures. Majority of end Ileostomy and all end colostomies are permanent and done on elective basis surgery. While temporary stomas mainly loop Ileostomy are done on an emergency basis in majority of the cases. There is strong correlation between emergency mode of surgery and Loop ileostomy with highly significant P value (<0.05). Out of 61 patients undergoing stoma construction, the most common indications for stoma construction was hollow viscous perforation (31.1%) followed by Enteric fever (18%) followed by GIT malignancy (11.5%) followed by carcinoma rectum (8.2%) followed by Koch's abdomen (6.6%) and stab injury abdomen (6.6%) followed by blunt trauma abdomen (3.3%), mesenteric ischemia (3.3%), adhesive intestinal obstruction (3.3%) and carcinoma anal canal (2.2%). Least no. of cases for ileocecal volvulus, necrotizing pancreatitis, volvulus gangrene, imperforated anus, high anorectal fistula, iatrogenic, refractory ulcerative colitis, strangulated hernia, anastomotic leak, abdominal sepsis 1.6% ($n=1$) each. Overall malignant cases were 11.5%, over all cases of trauma abdomen were 9.9%. These data are similar to study of Zeeshanuddin et

al Enteric fever (38%) followed by Koch's abdomen (18%) followed by GIT malignancy (13%). [9] Comparing to data of study of PORTER JA et al [10]; in 66 % cases of stoma cause was GIT malignancy and in 36% causes were benign, result of this study are different. The patients also assessed for secondary causes produced by primary pathology/disease for which intestinal stoma surgery done. The association between each of the 61 patients' stomas and the secondary reason of their creation was examined. It demonstrates a highly significant correlation ($p < 0.01$) between stoma construction and indication for stoma. Ileal perforation (52.5%) is most common secondary cause of intestinal stoma followed by intestinal obstruction (19.7%) followed by colonic perforation (6.6%). [9] In our study on 61 patients the most common type of stoma constructed was loop ileostomy in 41 (67.2%) cases followed by end ileostomy 10 (16.4%) followed by end sigmoid colostomy 7 (11.4%) out of these 7 end sigmoid colostomies, 6(9.8%) surgeries were done with abdomino-perineal resection mostly for carcinoma rectum and carcinoma anal canal and 1(1.6%) surgery was without abdominoperineal resection, followed by loop colostomy in 3 cases (4.9%). Total no. of ileostomies performed were 51(83.6%). Total no. of colostomies performed were 10(16.3%).

The data of other studies reveal similar results; study of AHMAD Z et al. [9] Total ileostomies performed were 76% and total colostomies were 21% and Jejunostomies were 3%. The association between the 61 patients' stomas and issues resulting from their construction was examined. It demonstrates a substantial correlation ($p < 0.05$) between the indication for a stoma and difficulties resulting from its construction. Forty-five of the 61 individuals in this study experienced issues linked to their stomas. In 28 cases (45.9%), skin excoriations were the most frequent consequence during stoma construction.

These were followed by laparotomy wound infection (14.8%), stoma retraction (9.8%), and stoma necrosis (1.6%). Skin excoriation occurred exclusively in 17 patients of intestinal stoma, in 5 patients it occurs along with laparotomy wound infection, in 4 cases it is with stomal retraction, in 1 case with parastomal abscess and in 1 case with stomal prolapse; so total 28 stoma cases associated with skin excoriation. Out of 41 loop ileostomies 21 developed skin excoriation and 8 cases developed laparotomy wound infection and 3 cases developed stomal retraction. Out of 7 end sigmoid colostomy patients 3 patients developed skin excoriation exclusively, 1 patient developed both wound infection and intestinal obstruction along with skin excoriation and 1 developed stomal retraction with skin excoriation. 2 patient of end

ileostomy developed stomal necrosis, burst abdomen occurred in 1 case of end ileostomy and 1 case of loop ileostomy. Comparison to data of study of Dushyant Rohit et al 108 on 56 stoma cases: results are nearly similar. [11] Regarding complications, results of this study are nearly similar or slightly differ with other previous studies on complications of intestinal stoma as skin excoriation is frequent complication followed by wound infection. [9,10] Conservative treatments such as endostomal therapy and skin care are used to manage the majority of the problems. However, a few issues, such as intestinal blockage and stomal retraction, require surgery. Comparing with study of Ana Livia de Oliveira et al [12] Of the 103 participants 63 (61.2%) had a colostomy and 40 (38.8%) had an ileostomy. For study they combined the both group and observed for Anthropometric measurements mainly BMI and body composition, which did not suggest nutritional deficiencies and did not differ significantly between groups, no significant correlation between nutritional derangement and stoma surgery: our study shows similar results. 61 patients' length of hospital stay was examined; the majority (72.1%) spent between 10 and 20 days in the hospital. 18% of patients spent more than 20 days in the hospital. 60% of patients in study Z Ahemad et al. spent 16–20 days in the hospital; the outcomes are comparable. Long hospital stays and related morbidity and problems are caused by stoma formation, which also indirectly raises costs.

Conclusion

According to the study's findings, stoma creation is more common in the adult and elderly age groups and is typically performed as an emergency treatment rather than an elective one. It was mostly used to divert blockage or perforation in cancer patients and trauma victims. Loop ileostomy and end ileostomy were the most often performed stomas. This is associated with a high risk of peristomal complications. Effective stoma care throughout the postoperative phase and appropriate preoperative planning improves the management of the problems.

References

1. Taylor P. An introduction to stomas: reasons for their formation. *Nurs Times* 2005; 101:63-4.
2. Irving MH, Hulme O. Intestinal stomas. *Br Med J* 1992; 304: 1679-81.
3. Shabbir J, Britton DC. Stoma complications: a literature overview. *Colorectal Dis off J Assoc Coloproctology G B Irel.* 2010 Oct; 12(10):958–64.
4. Saunders RN, Hemingway D. Intestinal Stomas. *Surg Int* 2005;71:44-7

5. Bhansali SK. Gastrointestinal perforations. A clinical study of 96 cases. *Journal of Postgraduate Medicine*. 1967; 13(1):1–12.
6. Krishnamurthy DM, Blatnik J, Mutch M. Stoma Complications. *Clin Colon Rectal Surg*. 2017; 30(3):193-200. doi:10.1055/s-0037-1598160
7. Person B, Ifargan R, Lachter J, Duek SD, Kluger Y, Assalia A. The impact of preoperative stoma site marking on the incidence of complications, quality of life, and patient's independence. *Dis Colon Rectum* 2012; 55:783–787.
8. Bhutra S, Singh A, Darwal R, Jain P, Kala V. A clinico-observational study of intestinal stoma and their complications. *International Surgery Journal*. 2019; 6(3):691.
9. Ahmad Z, Sharma A, Saxena P, Choudhary A, Ahmed M. A clinical study of intestinal stoma: its indications and complications. *International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*. 2013; 1(4):536.
10. Porter JA, Salvati EP, Rubin RJ, Eisenstat TE. Complications of colostomies. *Dis Colon Rectum*. 1989; 32(4):299-303. 108.
11. Dushyant Rohit , Sarvesh Jain , R S Verma, Grishmraj Pandey Temporary Loop Ileostomy for Ileal Perforation- A Surgical Experience of 56 Cases in a Resource Limited Setting. *Sch. J. App. Med. Sci.*, 2017; 5(5C):1931-1937.
12. De Oliveira AL, Boroni Moreira AP, Pereira Netto M, Gonçalves Leite IC. A Cross-sectional Study of Nutritional Status, Diet, and Dietary Restrictions among Persons with an Ileostomy or Colostomy. *Ostomy Wound Manage*. 2018; 64(5):18-29.